

Effect of *Pseudomonas* sp. on diesel and other petroleum fractions

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Abstract : The study examines the potential of bioremediation technologies to clean up oil spills in order to minimize the environmental pollution. The microorganism was isolated from an oil contaminated soil sample. The growth of this organism was observed to be maximum in Bushnell-Haas media containing 15% diesel at pH 7 within 3 days at 37 °C. The properties of this treated diesel was tested and compared with the untreated diesel. The experiment was also carried out for other petroleum fractions like Vacuum Gas Oil (VGO), Cycle Oil and Lube Oil.

Keywords : Bioremediation, Bushnell-Haas (BH) media, petroleum fractions.

Application of microbiology in the field of petroleum was reported in 1946¹, but it was only recently that scientists began focusing much of their attention towards microbial degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons². Fifteen bacterial strains isolated from solid waste oil samples were selected due to their capacity of growing in the presence of hydrocarbons. Growth of the strains in mineral liquid media supplemented with naphthalene, phenanthrene, fluoranthene or pyrene as sole carbon source was studied and our results showed that these strains can tolerate and remove different polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons that may be toxic in the environment polluted with hydrocarbons³.

Results and discussion

A microorganism was isolated from an oil contaminated soil sample no. 5. The suitability of this organism to utilize diesel fraction for its growth and other optimum conditions for better utilization of diesel was tested. Optimum pH for incubation for the organism 5A was found to be 7 in Bushnell-Haas media at 37 °C. At pH 7 (1% diesel) maximum growth was observed on third day.

Fresh subculture was done with the 5A organisms and 24 h culture was used to inoculate sterile BH media containing 3, 5, 7 and 9% diesel at pH 7. The flasks were kept in the incubator cum shaker at 37 °C for 3 days. After 3 days shaking, the flask containing 9% diesel showed maximum growth. The experiment was repeated with higher percentages of diesel. Results using

more than 15% diesel was not satisfactory. After 3 days, the conical flask containing 15% diesel was taken out from the incubator and the diesel separated from the liquid media. The properties of this diesel was tested and compared with the untreated diesel.

	Sp gr (15 °C)	C Residue (wt%)	S (wt%)	Aniline pt (°C)	Aromatic content (vol%)
Pure diesel	0.84	0.081	0.023	78	27.5
Treated diesel	0.8452	0.074	0.018	77.5	26.8

We can see that there is some change in the properties of the microorganism treated diesel from the pure diesel. The organism utilized the diesel for its growth in the media. Observing these we tested other petroleum fractions too like Vacuum Gas Oil (VGO), Cycle Oil and Lube Oil and the experiment was done in a similar manner as stated above. We used 5% of each fraction in the flask. After 3 days shaking in the incubator the maximum growth was found in VGO flask. The cycle oil-containing flask gave medium growth. But no significant growth was observed in the flask containing Lube Oil fraction.

From the study of physico-chemical properties of the diesel oil after three days treatment, it has been revealed that carbon residue, sulphur content, aniline point and aromatic content of the treated diesel has been reduced to some extent. It can therefore be concluded that the isolated microorganism was particularly suitable for degrading aromatics rather than paraffins as there was no such

growth in the lubricating oil medium of high viscosity index i.e. rich in paraffin.

Experimental

Sample collection : The work started with collection of oil contaminated soil samples from petrol pumps situated at different locations and microbial treatment on diesel was carried out by using these samples. Samples are : Bharat Petroleum Corporation Ltd., Airport Gate No. 1 (1), Khadinamore, Chinsura (2), Fariapukur (3), Sodepur, B. T. Road (4); Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Ltd., Fariapukur (5), Ultadanga Road (6), Sodepur, B. T. Road (7), Sukiya Street (8); Indian Oil Corporation Ltd., Khadinamore, Chinsura (9), Amherst Street (10).

Diesel, Vacuum Gas Oil (VGO), Cycle Oil, Lube Oil was provided by Indian Oil Corporation Ltd., Haldia, West Bengal, India. The liquid media used for the isolation of the microorganism was Bushnell-Haas media, which contains MgSO_4 , 0.2 g; CaCl_2 , 0.02 g; KH_2PO_4 , 1.0 g; K_2HPO_4 , 1.0 g; NH_4NO_3 , 1.0 g; FeCl_3 , 0.05 g (pH 7.0 $\pm$ 0.2 at 25 °C) per litre.

Isolation of organism :

Step-1 : Sterile 50 ml Bushnell-Haas (BH) media was taken in one of the flask (250 ml) and the other one (250 ml) was kept blank. 10 g of oil-contaminated soil was added to it aseptically and shaken for 5 min, allowed to settle (30 min) and the clear liquid media was decanted into the empty sterile conical flask. 1% diesel was added to it which served as the sole carbon source for microorganisms. The conical flask was incubated for 7 days at 37 °C in a shaker incubator when the liquid media turned hazy.

Step-2 : Isolation of the organism was done on nutrient agar (peptone 1%, NaCl 0.5%, Agar 1.5%, Beef extract 0.5%, per 100 ml pH 7.2–7.4) plates by streak plate method. Two single colonies were marked on the plate as A and B. Organisms from colonies A and B were separately isolated in two agar slants. These two steps were repeated for all the 10 samples and large number of organisms were isolated. Finally all the organisms were separately tested for best utilization of diesel using liquid BH medium and incubating at 37 °C for 7 days. Organism from sample number 5A showed best results and hence this organism was selected for all further studies. The organism 5A produces color in the media and from gram reaction and other preliminary studies it seemed that the organism may be pseudomonas species.

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